

EVALUATING THE INTEGRATION OF DISTRIBUTED TRACING SIGNALS INTO THE CERN MONITORING INFRASTRUCTURE

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PROJECT SPECIFICATION

The primary objective of this project is to create a proof-of-concept deployment of a distributed tracing system in such a way that it conforms to the standard practice rules the CERN monitoring infrastructure abides to. Additionally, steps towards integrating this proof-of-concept deployment with the current monitoring infrastructure should be taken. The secondary objective is to explore the possibilities for fully integrating distributed tracing into the CERN monitoring infrastructure in the future.

Key technologies

- **OpenTelemetry** - A set of APIs, SDKs and tooling that provides a unified approach for collecting and managing telemetry data (metrics, logs, and traces)
- **Jaeger Tracing** - An open-source, end-to-end distributed tracing framework that provides components for collecting, storing, and visualizing traces for monitoring and troubleshooting microservices-based distributed systems
- **Grafana** - A multi-platform open-source analytics and interactive visualization software

Major challenges

- **Distributed deployment** - The CERN infrastructure is a complex distributed system. The new distributed tracing subsystem has to tackle the challenges such an infrastructure poses, and ensure proper functionality, while involving a variety of components from different parts of the CERN infrastructure, often under different jurisdiction and overall different implementation methods and standards.
- **Secure communication channels** - Taking the previous point into account, ensuring communication within the new subsystem includes tackling challenges surrounding establishing secure channels for data transmission. This includes ensuring the usage of adequate modes of encryption, authentication and authorisation.
- **Numerous client connections** - As a part of the monitoring infrastructure, the new subsystem is client-oriented by nature. Thus, it must include components prepared to accommodate the needs of a large number of clients of different types which are present in the CERN system.

Project goals

- **Functionality and security** - As a result of this project, a system should be created such that it provides functionalities corresponding to the definition of distributed tracing. Additionally, the said system should conform to the security standards posed by the CERN infrastructure.
- **Enhanced visualization** - As a part of this project, advanced visualization tools should be used to ensure adequate utilization of the new monitoring data acquired through distributed tracing.
- **Effective diagnosis and resolution** - In order to solidify the significance of this project, an example of how to use the new distributed tracing data for efficient diagnosis of issues in a distributed system and their resolution should be provided.

ABSTRACT

Traditionally, infrastructures for system monitoring have been relying on logs and metrics as the telemetry data types gathered from a system about its behaviour. However, as systems are getting more and more complex every day, a need for collecting a more elaborate and informative telemetry data type called traces has arose. Traces are particularly useful for monitoring distributed systems, as they provide information about hierarchical and temporal dependencies between function invocations across different system components, as if all the invocations took place within a monolithic system, while also separating the concurrent/parallel invocation flows. Being one of the world's most complex scientific research environments, CERN has a particularly intricate distributed system in place. This provides solid grounds for believing that it could greatly benefit from the usage of distributed traces as an additional type of gathered telemetry data. Thus, this project revolves precisely around the integration of distributed tracing signals into the CERN monitoring infrastructure.

As a result of this project we have designed and implemented a distributed tracing infrastructure that conforms to development, structure and security related standards and rules used at CERN. The developed distributed tracing system has been connected to the CERN monitoring infrastructure and currently serves as a part of the *Monitoring-of-Monitoring (MoM)* portion of the infrastructure. The report details the technical challenges encountered during the development of this system and the methodologies employed to overcome them. These can serve as instructions or lessons to those who wish to develop a similar system. Additionally, this report contains a detailed analysis of the steps required to allow distributed tracing to be offered to all clients of the CERN monitoring system in a uniform manner, grouping together and unifying the handling of all three telemetry data types - logs, metrics and traces. This analysis includes several experiments aimed towards preparing the distributed tracing subsystem for its eventual full integration with the CERN monitoring infrastructure of the future. Furthermore, the report provides an in-depth examination of the options available for the visualization of traces. This examination emphasizes how these visualization options can be leveraged to enhance the quality of system monitoring.

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1 INTRODUCTION

In this section we aim to emphasize the need for elaborate system monitoring information and the transition from the traditional logs and metrics to traces, especially in the context of distributed systems. In the following sections, we describe the current state of the monitoring infrastructure at CERN and give a brief overview of the frameworks considered state-of-the-art for distributed tracing at the moment. Subsequently, we dive deep into the architectural makeup and deployment strategies of the system that is central for this report, after which we explore future prospects and potential shifts in the monitoring landscape. The document wraps up with a summary of key takeaways, supported by additional references and technical documentation.

A. MOTIVATION

In order to have high-quality system monitoring, we need elaborate information about the system's behaviour, coming from the system itself. Traditionally, systems have emitted this information in the form of logs and metrics. However, with the increased usage of distributed systems, a need for another type of telemetry data has appeared. Thus, **traces** were born.

Logs and metrics still carry immensely valuable information, even in distributed systems. Logs tell us about individual events that take place within each component, linking each event to its local context. This way, we get information about the event itself and some diagnostic/debugging metadata regarding the function within which this event took place. On the other hand, metrics provide an aggregated overview of system-level state over time. When relying solely on these two types of telemetry data, we end up with disconnected information. We can view the local events of each component separately, and we can view the impact they collectively have on the system, but we're missing the connection between them. The task of understanding the causality between the individual events and the resulting system state is left to the person attempting to interpret them. In a distributed system, analyzing logs from different components and trying to make sense of how they relate to one another and the system state, can be immensely difficult. Traces aim to solve this problem, and make distributed system monitoring easier and more elaborate. In order to understand exactly how traces aspire to do this, let's take a look at an example.

Figure 1: Example of a distributed system with logs and metrics [1]

In **Figure 1** we can see an example of a distributed system with 8 different components. Each of the components has some logs describing the events taking place within. Additionally, we have a metric depicting the system's state by showing the number of error messages per minute. Analyzing the system's behaviour by only looking at this set of information could be quite difficult. We would

need to analyze all logs from all components, trying to filter only the ones that lead to the error we can observe in the metric; then we would need to try to reason about how these events are connected and what the invocation chain that lead to their occurrence was. When using traces, we already get all of this information by default. In **Figure 2** we can see an example of the set of information we would get when using logs, metrics **and traces**. After observing in the metric that an error has occurred, we could use this information to filter user-level events and find that the *budget event b4382* caused the error. We could then choose to take a closer look at this budget event, and we would get the entire function invocation chain across the whole distributed system. This is depicted in **Figure 2** using blue arrows, where each of them is associated with a number in a blue circle with a solid boarder, showing the order of function invocations and returns representing the full invocation chain. For each of these invocations, we would get a list of logs, describing events that happened during their execution. In the aforementioned figure, these logs are underlined and highlighted in yellow, and each has an associated yellow square with dashed borders, containing a number, showing the function invocation the log is related to, and a letter, showing the order of the logs within that invocation.

Looking at this set of information, we immediately understand that it was the user *masa* that submitted a budget approval request, and that this caused an error because the *email* field for this user was empty. Additionally, this allows us to completely remove all ‘noise’ logs that have no impact on the current high-level event we’re observing. These logs are represented in the figure in light-gray with strike-through text.

In addition to the information depicted in **Figure 2**, traces give us the temporal dependencies between all function invocations that are a part of the same high-level event. This means that for function invocations 1 to 10 from this example, we would know exactly how long each of them took and in what point in time.

In summary, using traces in a distributed environment allows us to link together events from different components and view them in their order of occurrence, as if they were taking place in a monolithic system, while also separating the timelines of concurrent/parallel high-level events.

Figure 2: Example of a distributed system with logs, metrics and traces

Having its own data centers and a very large number of different tenants, applications and programs, the CERN computing infrastructure is an excellent example of an extremely complex distributed system. To keep track of what is going on in this system and promptly and adequately react to events of interest, as well as properly maintain this system, we need all the help we can get. By introducing traces to the CERN monitoring infrastructure, we would increase the verbosity of information we get from the computing infrastructure, allowing us to provide better care and maintenance for it.

2 CURRENT MONITORING INFRASTRUCTURE

In this section we will take a brief look at the current monitoring infrastructure. A high-level overview of the current state will help us understand how the new elements will fit in, and will provide us with a framework to think about the evolution of the infrastructure and next steps.

The current monitoring infrastructure provides support for logs, metrics and alarms throughout their entire lifespan - from the point of origin and collection to storage and visualization. The detailed visual overview of this infrastructure can be seen in **Figure 3**.

The central component of the system is **Kafka** [2], all of the monitoring data passes through it. **Kafka** is then surrounded by the ingestion layer on one side and the sink/export layer on the other.

Figure 3: Visual overview of the current monitoring infrastructure [3]

Monitoring data can originate from clients (client applications) or from machines in the data center. In order to collect the monitoring data from the machines, each one is equipped with the "monit-bundle", consisting of **Collectd** [4] and **Fluent Bit** [5]. **Collectd** is a daemon responsible for scraping monitoring data from the operating system and **Fluent Bit** serves as a connector to the remainder of the monitoring infrastructure and a short-time buffer. By buffering data at this stage, we ensure its safety in case of short-term failure of the monitoring infrastructure. **Fluent Bit** is a relatively new component of the "monit-bundle", and the transition towards its complete integration in the monitoring system is not yet fully completed. Thus, not all data center machines use it to connect to the remainder of the monitoring infrastructure at this point, but efforts are currently being made towards making this a reality in the near future.

All monitoring data is collected by the **Flume** [6] ingestion instance. This collector is both push and pull based. The reason for this is that although clients can push data by using an endpoint, sources like message queues require data to be pulled from them. Along with the data collection, this instance also ensures the conversion of data from the client format to the standardized JSON schema used inside the monitoring infrastructure. Subsequently, the component pushes all data to an adequate **Kafka** topic, based on the tenant it originated from.

Kafka serves as a bridge to the remainder of the infrastructure, also ensuring short-term persistence of the data in flight. Being the central point in the infrastructure, **Kafka** is also the place where the processing pipeline is attached. Both the data in streaming and in batch format can be read from **Kafka** and processed based on the specific needs (e.g. enriched or aggregated), and written back.

On the other side of **Kafka** is the sink/export layer. It consists of **Kafka Connect** and **Flume**. **Kafka Connect** ensures the transition of data from **Kafka** to **HDFS** [7] and is used specifically for the monitoring data coming from the data center nodes themselves. This data has a static schema and can be exported this way. By storing it in **HDFS**, we make the data available for others to view in raw format if needed. **Flume** is used as the more general exporter. It reads data from **Kafka** and ensures its conversion from the internal monitoring schema to the format required for storing/visualization. Subsequently, the data from **Flume** is used to raise alarms if applicable, and is sent to storage.

Depending on the specific needs, the data is stored in **HDFS**, **InfluxDB** [8] and/or **OpenSearch** [9], from where it can be read and visualized. The time-series data stored in **InfluxDB** (along with additional data from sources outside the monitoring infrastructure) is used to check the compliance with SLIs and is visualized in **Grafana** [10]. The data from **OpenSearch** can be visualized both in **Grafana** and the **OpenSearch** dashboard. And for accessing and viewing data from **HDFS**, a platform called **SWAN** [11] is used. This is a platform created at CERN, for performing interactive data analysis in the cloud.

The previously described infrastructure has served for monitoring purposes at CERN for some time (and is still serving), but there is ongoing effort to restructure it, which we will discuss more in **Section 6**. Due to this, the newest part of the infrastructure, consisting of **Prometheus** [12] and **Grafana Mimir** [13], is linked directly to the visualization layer, bypassing the remainder of the infrastructure. As the transition to the new form is slowly made, this part will be uniformly integrated as well.

3 DISTRIBUTED TRACING STATE-OF-THE-ART

In order to introduce distributed tracing into our infrastructure, we would like to utilize open-source frameworks widely used in the industry. Since distributed tracing has been around long enough, industry has converged towards a standard - using **OpenTelemetry** [14] and **Jaeger Tracing** [15].

A. OPENTELEMETRY

OpenTelemetry (OTel) is a framework for creating and managing telemetry data. It supports metrics, logs and traces. It has become an industry standard for telemetry data because it provides [16]:

- Semantic conventions that define a standard naming scheme for common telemetry data types
- A standard protocol for telemetry data - OTLP (**OpenTelemetry Protocol**)
- Language SDKs that implement the specification, APIs, and export of telemetry data
- A library ecosystem that implements instrumentation for common libraries and frameworks
- Automatic instrumentation components that generate telemetry data without requiring code changes
- APIs that define how to generate telemetry data yourself
- The **OpenTelemetry Collector** - a proxy that receives, processes, and exports telemetry data

As can be concluded by looking at the list above, **OpenTelemetry** provides comprehensive support for creating, gathering and managing telemetry data. **OpenTelemetry** is also a Cloud Native Computing Foundation (CNCF) project.

B. JAEGER TRACING

Jaeger is a distributed tracing platform, providing components and infrastructure needed to use traces in your distributed system. Jaeger provides native integration with OpenTelemetry and the OTLP protocol. Even more so, the Jaeger SDKs have been deprecated in favour of the OpenTelemetry SDKs. Jaeger provides the following components:

- **Collector** - Serves as a collection point for traces. It receives them, checks their validity, processes them and stores them in a storage backend. For production environments, the storage can be Cassandra, Elasticsearch/OpenSearch, or a remote storage integrated through gRPC.
- **Query** - Serves as the presentation point for traces. It exposes the APIs for retrieving traces from the storage backend and hosts the Jaeger UI for searching and analyzing traces.
- **Agent** - This is a deprecated component. It was made to integrate with the Jaeger SDKs. It is designed to be deployed close to the client and abstract away the specifics of establishing and maintaining the connection to the Collector. It is not a mandatory component, as even the Jaeger SDKs can be configured to contact the Collector directly.
- **Ingester** - A stripped-down version of the Collector used when data is ingested exclusively from Kafka. It reads the traces from Kafka and writes them to the configured storage backend.

4 DEPLOYMENT AND INFRASTRUCTURE

Having described the details of the current monitoring infrastructure at CERN in **Section 2**, and the motivation behind introducing distributed tracing signals to it in **Section 1.A.**, now is the time to talk about how this introduction was actually done. In the remainder of this section we will show the infrastructure of the distributed tracing system, explain its components, their locations and the way they connect to one another, and talk about the challenges we faced when deploying this system.

A. THE ARCHITECTURE OF THE DISTRIBUTED TRACING SYSTEM

The goal of this project was to create a proof-of-concept deployment of a distributed tracing infrastructure that will follow the guidelines and rules used by the CERN monitoring team, and would thus be prepared to eventually be fully integrated into the monitoring infrastructure at CERN.

The visual overview of the resulting infrastructure can be seen in **Figure 4**. In this figure, the existing parts of the monitoring infrastructure are depicted in orange, with dashed borders; the newly deployed elements are depicted in blue, with solid borders; and the elements maintained outside of the monitoring team are depicted in black/gray, with borders following the dash-dot pattern. Each cluster is represented by a rectangle of different color, with a dotted boarder. The connections between components are represented with lines, where the black solid lines represent communication conducted without any encryption, and the green dashed lines represent communication encrypted using TLS. Each connection also has an associated label, containing a colon followed by a number, showing which port is used to establish it. When a cluster boundary is 'cut' with a component, that component depicts a port opened to the outside world; and the writing inside the component shows which type of authentication is used in order to establish a connection using that port. In the case when a component contained inside a cluster has a narrow wall on one of its sides, through which it makes connections, this means that the connection is made through a service, rather than to the component directly.

The distributed tracing infrastructure has 2 entry points - one for gathering tracing data, and one for presenting the results and visualizations. This means it also has two types of clients, for which we will introduce the following terminology:

Figure 4: Visual overview of the distributed tracing system's architecture

- *client producer* - the client generating the tracing data
- *client consumer* - the client querying the system to get access to the accumulated tracing data and its visualizations

i. Core of the system

In order to facilitate the handling of tracing data throughout its entire life cycle, the system relies on the components from Jaeger Tracing, described in **Section 3.B.**. The core of the system consist of the Jaeger Collector and the Jaeger Query. The Jaeger Collector is the main entry point for the *client producer*, whereas the Jaeger Query is the main entry point for the *client consumer*. The *client producer* pushes the tracing data to the Jaeger Collector, which ensures it is properly formatted and stores it to permanent storage. When the *client consumer* wants to access the system, it does so thought the Jaeger Query component, which accepts the user query, processes it, accesses the necessary data in permanent storage, formats the response and sends it back to the requester.

Since the two components contained in the core are tracing-specific, we decided to place them together, inside an OpenShift cluster dedicated for the needs of the distributed tracing infrastructure. This solution gives us the ability to centrally control the core of the distributed tracing infrastructure through an elaborate UI, with the possibility of using high-level abstractions for handling the necessary cluster management needs.

ii. Permanent storage

As mentioned in **Section 3.B.**, Jaeger Tracing can use one of the following options as a storage backend - Cassandra, Elasticsearch/OpenSearch, or a remote storage integrated through gRPC. Within the CERN monitoring team, it is standard practice to use OpenSearch for storing monitoring data. This is why we opted for this type of storage for tracing data as well. All OpenSearch clusters used by the monitoring team are created and managed by another team at CERN, responsible for storage. In order to separate the new type of monitoring data from the existing ones, so that we can properly test the new infrastructure, we requested a new OpenSearch cluster from the storage team. After this cluster was created, access to it was given to the e-group representing the monitoring

team, through the CERN Single-Sign-On (SSO) system. After accessing the cluster this way, we were able to create internal users in order to enable cluster access using basic authentication. These newly created internal users represent the core components of the distributed tracing infrastructure, as these components will be the ones using them to access the permanent storage.

iii. Clients

In order to be able to test the entire distributed tracing infrastructure, we needed to select a *client producer* that will generate the tracing data which will be used by the remainder of the system. For this job, we chose **Grafana Mimir**. **Grafana Mimir** is one of the existing components of the monitoring infrastructure, it is used as permanent storage for **Prometheus** data. It is a valuable part of the existing infrastructure, and the ability to collect and use its tracing data would be incredibly useful. **Grafana Mimir** uses a deprecated **Jaeger SDK** for Golang. This is why we require another deprecated **Jaeger** component to ensure its connection to the remainder of the system - the **Jaeger Agent**. This component is used in order to hide the details of establishing a connection from the client application to the **Jaeger Collector**. The **Jaeger Agent** is meant to be deployed closely to the client application, which is why those two components are located in the same cluster. The exact method of connecting the *client producer* to the remainder of the distributed tracing infrastructure depends on the implementation of the client itself. Thus, this part of the infrastructure was adapted to the current implementation of **Grafana Mimir**. This will be discussed in further detail in **Section 6**, where we will analyze how this part of the infrastructure can potentially be changed in order to enable all monitoring data to be gathered in a uniform way in the future.

Another *client producer* is the distributed tracing system itself. The system has the ability to collect its own tracing data and thus allow better insight into the details of its functionality. In order to enable this, the **Jaeger Query** component has an attached **Jaeger Agent** which ensures a connection to the **Jaeger Collector** and the proper collection of the tracing data from within the system itself.

In our case, the *client consumers* are web clients. They can query the tracing data and view its visualizations through the **Jaeger UI** - a web interface offered by the **Jaeger Query** component. We have also explored the possibility of visualizing tracing data through **Grafana**. Details about this are explored separately in **Section 5**.

iv. Connecting the components

The system for distributed tracing is a distributed system itself. Its components are located in different clusters, with different maintainers. The core of the system is located in one cluster, permanent storage in another, and *client producers* and *client consumers* can be located anywhere inside CERN. This is why great care had to be taken when establishing connections between all of the different components of the distributed tracing infrastructure. These connections had to be properly secured, with adequate authentication and encryption where necessary.

The connection between a *client producer* and its **Jaeger Agent** is one of the simpler ones. These two components are considered to be tightly coupled and should always be located in the same cluster. This is why this connection can be established without any encryption or authentication. The *client producer* connects to its **Jaeger Agent** through UDP, using the cluster-local address of the service representing the **Jaeger Agent** and the port 6831, which is the default port used by the **Agent** for client-connections.

The connection between the **Jaeger Agent** and the **Jaeger Collector** is more tricky. This connection potentially crosses the cluster boundaries and thus has to be properly secured. It is established through gRPC, and in our specific case doesn't require any authentication, since the *client producers* used are under the same jurisdiction as the monitoring infrastructure itself. However, since this connection crosses cluster boundaries, it does require encryption, which is why TLS is used. The

default **Jaeger Collector** port for linking to the **Jaeger Agent** through gRPC is 14250. In order to enable the establishment of a TLS connection through this port, an endpoint needs to be adequately exposed to the outside world. This endpoint needs to possess a TLS certificate, used to identify it to the clients attempting to establish a connection. Additionally, the **Jaeger Agent** needs to have access to the information about the certificate authority responsible for issuing the said certificate. Since this communication is secure, it is conducted over HTTPS. Thus, for exposing the **Jaeger Collector** endpoint, the default HTTPS port is used - 443.

As explained previously in **Section 4.A.ii.**, the creation of the permanent storage cluster is the responsibility of a dedicated team. Once the **OpenSearch** cluster used in this infrastructure was created, the access to it was granted to the CERN monitoring team through the CERN SSO. After this, we were able to create a new internal client with access rights. This internal client was then used to represent the **Jaeger Query** and **Jaeger Collector** components when they try to access permanent storage. Since the permanent storage is located in a dedicated cluster, accessing it crosses cluster boundaries. That is why the connections to it are encrypted, using the TLS protocol. The **OpenSearch** cluster uses the CERN Grid Certificate to identify itself as a part of the CERN Computing Grid. That is why the **Jaeger Query** and the **Jaeger Collector** need the CERN Grid Certificate Authority certificate in order to be able to validate it. In order to establish a connection to permanent storage, the **Jaeger** components access the **OpenSearch** cluster at the default port for HTTPS, port 443.

Possibly the trickiest connection to make was the one connecting the *client consumers* to the distributed tracing infrastructure. These clients are web clients, accessing the **Jaeger UI**, provided by the **Jaeger Query** component. At CERN, the common practice for accessing a web service is to conduct the user authentication using the CERN SSO. This ensures that a user desiring to access multiple CERN web services can log in only once and automatically be granted access to all allowed services. In order to conform to this standard, we needed an additional component in the distributed tracing infrastructure - an **SSO proxy** component. This component ensures that proper credentials are provided before forwarding the traffic to the **Jaeger Query**. The **SSO proxy** is tightly coupled with the **Jaeger Query**, which is why the two of them are deployed in the same cluster. Due to this, the connection between the two can be done without any authentication or encryption. The **SSO proxy** contacts the **Jaeger Query** by using the cluster local address of the service in front of it, and the default HTTP port, port 80. In addition to this, the access to the **SSO proxy** needs to be enabled to the world outside the cluster. In order to do this, an endpoint with SSO authentication and TLS encryption must be created. This endpoint allows access to the **SSO proxy** at port 4180, which is the default port used by this proxy for this type of communication. The endpoint is meant to be used by web clients, and since it uses secure communication, it is established using the default HTTPS port, port 443.

B. DEPLOYMENT METHODS

In this subsection we will discuss the methods used to deploy the new components of the distributed tracing infrastructure described above.

i. Jaeger Query and Jaeger Collector

The currently most widely used method for deploying **Jaeger** components is using a **Jaeger Operator**. However, this wasn't the best solution in our case. Namely, in order to have the ability to use an Operator within a CERN OpenShift cluster, it would have to be installed for all OpenShift users CERN-wide. In order to avoid this, we opted for deploying the **Jaeger Query** and **Jaeger Collector** using a Helm chart provided specifically for **Jaeger Tracing** [17]. The modifications made to the `values.yaml` file used for the deployment can be seen in **Listing 1**.

In this configuration file we have the following values:

- `<opensearch_cluster_address>` - The address of the OpenSearch cluster used for permanent storage
- `<os_internal_user_name>` - The name of the internal user used to access the OpenSearch cluster used for permanent storage
- `<os_internal_user_password_secret_name>` - The name of the secret holding the password for the internal user used to access the OpenSearch cluster used for permanent storage
- `<os_internal_user_password_secret_key>` - The name of the key under which the password is stored inside the secret `<os_internal_user_password_secret_name>`
- `<OS_CA_Certificate_secret>` - The name of the secret holding the Certificate Authority Certificate needed to validate the certificate received from the OpenSearch cluster
- `<jaeger_collector_hostname>` - The hostname of the Jaeger Collector component
- `<collector_TLS_secret_name>` - The name of the secret holding the details about the certificate used by the Jaeger Collector to prove its identity when a Jaeger Agent tries to establish a TLS encrypted connection to it
- `<collector_TLS_secret_RSA_key>` - The name of the key under which the RSA key is stored inside the secret `<collector_TLS_secret_name>`
- `<collector_TLS_secret_certificate_key>` - The name of the key under which the certificate is stored inside the secret `<collector_TLS_secret_name>`

Using the configuration file `values.yaml`, described in **Listing 1**, the deployment was done using the following steps:

```
$ helm repo add jaegertracing https://jaegertracing.github.io/helm-charts
$ helm repo update
$ helm install jaeger jaegertracing/jaeger --values values.yaml
```

ii. Route to the Jaeger Collector

In order to enable *client producers* to send their tracing data over TLS to the Jaeger Collector, through the means of the Jaeger Agent, we need to create an appropriate route inside the OpenShift cluster. This route has to possess an appropriate TLS certificate, such that the Collector can prove its identity to the clients attempting to connect to it. In order to facilitate this, we created 3 new resources inside the OpenShift cluster - an Issuer, a Certificate and a Route. The configuration file used for the creation of these resources can be seen in **Listing 2**.

In this configuration file, we have the following values:

- `<acme_private_key_secret_name>` - The name of the secret holding the details about the credentials needed to access the private account of the service used for the certificate generation
- `<encryption_server_address>` - The address of the server used to generate the necessary TLS certificate
- `<jaeger_collector_hostname>` - The hostname of the Jaeger Collector component, under which the route will be exposed

- `<collector_TLS_secret_name>` - The name of the secret holding the details about the certificate used by the **Jaeger Collector** to prove its identity when a **Jaeger Agent** tries to establish a TLS encrypted connection to it

Using the previously described configuration file, the deployment of the necessary resources was done with the following command:

```
$ kubectl apply -f collector-route.yaml
```

Out of the resources generated in such a way the **Issuer** resource describes the method used to generate the necessary certificate, the **Certificate** resource describes the certificate itself and the **Route** resource describes the **Jaeger Collector** endpoint exposed outside the OpenShift cluster boundaries.

iii. Jaeger Agent

The **Jaeger Agent** had to be deployed in a Kubernetes cluster, close to the *client producer* application **Grafana Mimir**. To facilitate this, we created a Kubernetes **Deployment** for the **Jaeger Agent** component, whose configuration can be seen in **Listing 3**, and a Kubernetes **Service** for establishing connections to that component, whose configuration can be seen in **Listing 4**.

In these configuration files, we have the following values:

- `<client_producer_namespace>` - The name of the Kubernetes namespace in which the *client producer* resides
- `<jaeger_collector_hostname>` - The hostname of the **Jaeger Collector** component

Using the previously described configuration files, the deployment was done using the following steps:

```
$ kubectl apply -f jaeger-agent-deployment.yaml
$ kubectl apply -f jaeger-agent-service.yaml
```

In addition to the previously described configuration, in order to enable the connection between **Grafana Mimir** and the **Jaeger Agent**, we needed to alter the **Grafana Mimir** deployment in such a way that it now has the following environment variables:

- `JAEGER_AGENT_HOST=jaeger-agent-service.<client_producer_namespace>.svc.cluster.local`
- `JAEGER_AGENT_PORT='6831'`

iv. SSO proxy and route to the SSO proxy

The **SSO proxy** and the corresponding route had to be deployed inside an OpenShift cluster. For this purpose, we used the '*CERN Auth Proxy v0.4.0*' Helm chart. This chart is installed for all CERN OpenShift users and can be used through the OpenShift Web Console. This chart was created for authentication purposes and to be used inside CERN only, thus its configuration files are not publicly accessible. The chart ensures the creation of the **SSO proxy Deployment**, a corresponding **Service** and an adequate **Route** for exposing it to the outside world. The deployment of the chart was done through the OpenShift Web Console and the following parameters were used:

- **Service name:** `jaeger-query`
- **Port:** `80`
- **Public Application Hostname:** `<route_web_address>`

- **Create a route:** true
- **Application subpath:** /
- **Internet Visibility:** false
- **Route Annotations:** None
- **Authentication options:**
 - **Allowed role:** default-role
 - **Oauth Proxy Prefix:** /oauth2
 - **Prefer Email Address:** true
 - **Extra Arguments:** None

These parameters define that the **Service** of the application which needs the SSO proxy is called **jaeger-query**, and is supposed to be contacted at port 80. Additionally, they state that a route should be created, with the address `<route_web_address>`, without a subpath or any route annotations. This route will not be visible on the whole internet, but only within the CERN network. The authentication options used were the default values for the CERN Auth Proxy.

5 RESULTS

In order to properly make use of the generated traces, we need a way to visualize them. For this, **Jaeger Tracing** natively offers **Jaeger UI** within the **Query** component. Additionally, we decided to explore the possibilities of integrating traces into **Grafana**, with the goal of unifying the way we present monitoring data to our clients.

In the remainder of this section we will first take a look at the visualization options **Jaeger UI** and **Grafana** have to offer. Then, we will compare the advantages and disadvantages of one over the other. And finally, we will take a look at one specific client application, and explore the use cases in which traces and their visualizations can help us understand what is going on within.

A. JAEGER UI

The **Jaeger Query** component provides a native interactive visualization environment for traces called **Jaeger UI**. The home page of **Jaeger UI** can be seen in **Figure 5**. We can analyze the capabilities of this UI through the enumerated points from the figure:

1. **Search** - Enables finding a set of traces that satisfy some specific set of criteria. The options based on which you can search are:
 - *Service* - The name of the service that was a part of the trace. When generating the trace, applications usually use this field to store the name of the system component executing the current function.
 - *Operation* - The name of the function that was invoked as a part of the trace.
 - *Tags* - A whitespace-separated list of *'key = value'* pairs that must be present in the meta-data of the trace.
 - *Lookback* - The time frame of interest. You can either choose one of the default options (e.g. *Last Hour*, *Last 6 Hours* etc.) or define a custom time range.
 - *Start Time* and *End Time* - If a custom time range is chosen, then a start and an end time and date must be specified.
 - *Max Duration* and *Min Duration* - The limitations as to how long should have the whole trace taken.

- *Limit results* - Specifying whether to show all traces that match the search criteria, or only the top *x* results.
2. **Lookup by Trace ID** - Enables searching for a specific trace based on its ID.
 3. **Upload** - Allows you to upload a JSON file containing one or more traces, and see their visualizations.
 4. **Trace distribution** - As a part of the results, you can see the distribution of the selected traces over time, along with how long each of them took to complete.
 5. **List of traces** - As a part of the results, you get a list of traces. Each of them shows the name of the top-most invoked function of the trace and the name of the system component that was executing it; the total number of function invocations (spans) the trace contains; the list of system components that were involved in the execution of the entire trace; the duration of the trace; and the trace start time stamp.
 6. **Deep Dependency Graph** - Based only on the traces that are a part of the generated result, a graph is created to depict the dependencies between the system components involved in the execution of those traces.

Figure 5: Jaeger UI - home page

By clicking on one of the traces from the list, you access the individual trace visualization, an example of which can be seen in **Figure 6**. The left part of the visualization shows the hierarchical dependencies between function invocations (spans), and the right part shows the temporal dependencies.

The hierarchical dependencies show which function was invoked by which function and inside which system component. And the temporal dependencies show at what point in time has each invocation taken place and how long it lasted.

Clicking on a function invocation of interest shows its attached metadata - the *Tags* show metadata attached specifically to that function invocation, *Process* shows information about the executor of the function and *Logs* give information about events that happened during the execution of this function.

The visualization visible in the figure is only one of the offered options. In the top right corner there is a drop-down menu with other visualization options, including graph, statistics, table, JSON and flame graph. One of the most interesting options is the graph visualization, an example of which can be seen in **Figure 7**. This visualization option shows the function invocation dependencies in the form of a graph, where the parent node represents the invoker and the child nodes represent the functions being invoked by the parent. Additionally, each node in the graph has a color that indicates the system component that was executing the function the node represents.

Figure 6: Jaeger UI - visualizing a trace

Figure 7: Jaeger UI - trace graph

B. GRAFANA

In order to connect Grafana to the Jaeger ecosystem, we created a Jaeger data source in Grafana. The basic configuration of this data source includes specifying the URL leading to the Jaeger Query component and the adequate authentication credentials for accessing it. Details about the possibilities for additional configuration can be found in **Section 5.B.i.**

Using the created data source, we can utilize the following three types of queries - *Search*, *TraceID* and *JSON File*. *Search* provides the same set of options as the *Search* query type from Jaeger UI,

while the results are presented differently. The results of such a query in **Grafana** are presented as a table containing the ID, name, start time and duration of each trace that satisfies the specified search criteria. By clicking on one of the IDs from the table, or by using the query type *TraceID*, we get a trace visualization similar to the one provided by **Jaeger UI**. This visualization can be seen in **Figure 8**. The main difference between the two visualizations is the naming scheme of the metadata categories - *Tags* from **Jaeger** map to *Attributes* in **Grafana**, *Process* maps to *Resource* and *Logs* map to *Events*. The query type *JSON File* allows us to upload a JSON file containing a trace and immediately visualize it as if we were using the *TraceID* query.

Figure 8: Grafana - query of type *TraceID*

i. Additional configurations

In order to fully utilize all of the possibilities **Grafana** has to offer for the visualization of traces, some additional configuration is required. This includes enabling the usage of the node graph and linking the traces to the associated logs [18].

The node graph is a beta feature of the **Jaeger** data source in **Grafana**. It enables trace visualization in the form of a graph, in addition to the default visualization. An example can be seen in **Figure 9**.

Linking the traces to the associated logs is a feature that adds a button "*Logs for this span*" to each span in the result of a trace query, which should allow access to the set of logs associated with the initial span. In order to configure this feature, one must set up the required fields in the "*Trace to logs*" section of the **Jaeger** data source in **Grafana**. The fields include:

- **Data source** - The **Grafana** data source for the storage containing the logs, selected from a drop-down menu.
- **Span start time shift** and **Span end time shift** - Since the timestamp from the event within the trace and the timestamp from the log might not exactly match, we need to define a time window around the timestamp from the trace event in which we will search for the corresponding log. **Span start time shift** defines the beginning of that window, and **Span end time shift** defines the end.
- **Tags** - Defines the mapping between trace metadata field names and the log field names. It is a list of elements defined as "*<x> as <y>*", where *<x>* is the name of the metadata field in the trace and *<y>* is the name of the corresponding field in the log.
- A set of fields defining how to identify the adequate log, based on the initial trace:

- **Use custom query** - A toggle field. If enabled, a query defining how to find the appropriate log must be defined, and the fields **Filter by trace ID** and **Filter by span ID** must be disabled.
- **Filter by trace ID** - A toggle field. If enabled, the log will be selected by making sure that the value of the field *traceID* within it is equal to the ID of the initial trace.
- **Filter by span ID** - A toggle field. If enabled, the log will be selected by making sure that the value of the field *spanID* within it is equal to the ID of the initial span.
- **Query** - If **Use custom query** is enabled, this field should contain the query needed to identify the correct log. When writing the query one can access - the fields in the log, by simply writing their name; the metadata from the trace, by using $\${_trace.<x>}$, where $<x>$ is the name of the metadata field; and the list specified within **Tags** by using $\${_tags}$.

The settings used to configure the link in our case were the following:

- **Data source** = `monit-timberprivate` - The data source leading to the OpenSearch instance storing all logs.
- **Span start time shift** = `-5m` - Starting the search 5 minutes before the time from the timestamp included in the event from the trace.
- **Span end time shift** = `5m` - Ending the search 5 minutes after the time from the timestamp included in the event from the trace.
- **Tags** = `hostname as data.kubernetes.pod_name` - Mapping the *hostname* filed from the trace metadata to the *data.kubernetes.pod_name* field from the logs.
- **Use custom query** = `true` - In our case, the logs don't contain neither the "*traceID*", nor the "*spanID*" fields at the topmost level, so we must define our own way of identifying the correct log.
- **Filter by trace ID** = `false`
- **Filter by span ID** = `false`
- **Query** = $\${_tags}$ AND `data.raw.traceID=${_trace.traceId}` - This query ensures that the fields whose mapping was defined in **Tags** match in value and that the field *data.raw.traceID* from the logs matches the ID from the trace.

C. COMPARING THE VISUALIZATIONS

Even though both **Jaeger UI** and **Grafana** offer similar basic trace visualizations, there are some specificities that give one advantage over the other.

Jaeger UI seems to be better adapted to the specific task of visualizing traces. The initial view containing the distribution of traces satisfying the search parameters over time and their respective duration is very helpful as an instant overview of the situation. Additionally, the fact that the initial view of each trace contains the list of components involved in it can be very helpful in immediately understanding the context of the trace. In the case when there are many spans within a trace, the **Grafana** node graph quickly becomes very unreadable, with too many nodes overwhelming the viewer; whereas in **Jaeger UI**, the granularity of the graph is moderated such that the amount of presented information is always manageable, and the design of the graph itself is more understandable, due to the ability to distinguish the spans from different components through different colors.

Figure 9: Grafana - visualization in the form of a node graph

An additional advantage of Jaeger UI over Grafana is a larger number of different visualizations available - you can easily access the trace statistics and view how much time is spent in each component in the current trace, on average, and in the extreme (minimum and maximum); you can view the flame graph visualization of each trace; and you can easily access the graph presenting invocation dependencies with component-level granularity, based on the currently selected set of traces. These possibilities are not provided out of the box in Grafana.

However, Grafana has one big advantage, and that is the possibility to link a trace directly to the set of logs it is related to. The logs often carry very valuable information with regard to what exactly is going on in the system, and the ability to access the relevant ones at the click of a button gives traces a significant boost in power.

D. CLIENTS AND THE APPLICABILITY OF TRACING

In order to understand how exactly traces can help us in a real-world scenario, let's take a look at one specific client application and some of its use-cases. The application chosen is Grafana Mimir. It is one of the newest components of the monitoring ecosystem, and as discussed in Section 2, it was not uniformly linked to the existing infrastructure due to current restructuring efforts. This makes it a good candidate to be connected to the experimental monitoring elements.

i. Grafana Mimir

Grafana Mimir offers long-term storage for Prometheus data. The high-level overview of the system architecture can be seen in Figure 10. The system consists of 6 mandatory component types - *query-frontend*, *querier*, *distributor*, *ingester*, *store-gateway* and *compactor*; and 4 optional component types - *query-scheduler*, *ruler*, *alertmanager* and *overrides-exporter* (not pictured). The deployment of Grafana Mimir within the monitoring infrastructure contains all 10 component types.

In order to be able to analyze tracing use-cases, we will provide a high-level overview of the read and write paths of our Grafana Mimir instance. Further information about the details of how Grafana Mimir works can be found in the documentation [13].

The first component encountered on the **read path** is the *query-frontend*. This component accepts the query, and if it addresses a long time span, splits it into multiple smaller queries. For each of the smaller queries, the *query-frontend* checks whether the result can be found in local cache. If it can, the processing of this sub-query is finished here. If it can't, the *query-frontend* sends the query to the

Figure 10: Grafana Mimir - overview of the system architecture

query-scheduler, where it is placed into one of multiple FIFO (First In, First Out) queues. The system contains multiple instances of the *querier* component. These act as workers, and each periodically pulls queries waiting in the queues inside the *query-scheduler*. When the *querier* takes a query, it analyses which type of data does this query need. The data that was recently written is accessed through the *ingester*, whereas the data from long-term storage is accessed through the *store-gateway*. The *ingester* has temporary storage for recently written data, which it periodically writes to long-term storage.

The write requests are accepted by the *distributor*. It first checks the validity of received data, as well as the limits associated with the tenant attempting to write. The data that satisfies the initial conditions is then divided into batches and replicated. Such created data chunks are then sent to multiple *ingester* components in parallel, where they are initially stored in temporary storage and after some time written to long-term storage as well.

ii. Exploring use-cases

Knowing the basics about how Grafana Mimir functions, let's take a look at how traces can help us be more informed about how it is used.

One use-case could be **keeping track of data rejected by the distributor**. In order to do this, we can create a query in either Grafana or Jaeger UI with the following parameters:

- Service: `mimir-distributor`
- Operation: `/cortex.Ingester/Push`
- Tags: `error=true`

Querying Jaeger UI instantly gives us the distribution of the erroneous calls to the selected function within the *distributor* over time, as can be seen in **Figure 11**. Additionally, each of the traces shows us the number of errors that took place within, providing a quick overview of the situation. After

clicking on the desired trace, we are able to use the search bar at the top right to look for the keyword "error" and be guided to all points in the trace containing an error message. Opening the content of the contained logs shows us the tenant which caused the rejection of data and the reason for rejection, as can be seen in **Figure 12**.

Figure 11: Keeping track of data rejected by the *distributor*, initial view

Another use-case could be **understanding the queries received by the system and their impact**. In order to have an overview of the queries received by the system, we can query either Grafana or Jaeger UI with the following parameters:

- Service: `mimir-query-frontend`
- Operation: `/frontendv2pb.FrontendForQuerier/QueryResult`

When using Jaeger UI, the initial overview already gives us a list of components each of the traces touched, allowing an easy check of how many queries use data that is not recent (have to go through the *store-gateway*). Additionally, the initial overview gives us the number of spans each trace contains, providing us with a taste of the complexity of each query. By clicking on a trace of interest, we can get more detailed information. The top-most span gives us the query that initiated the trace. If using Grafana, we can click the "Logs for this span" button and see the full details of the query event, including the tenant that requested it. On the other hand, if using Jaeger UI, we can take a look at the trace graph and understand the flow of invocations the query caused inside the system. In any case, by looking at the trace visualization itself, we get the complete hierarchical structure of the internal system calls, as well as their temporal dependencies, as can be seen in previously provided examples in **Figure 6** and **Figure 8**. By analyzing these dependencies and looking into the metadata of spans that interest us, we can fully understand what kind of an impact a query had to the system. The information goes as far as showing the exact IDs of blocks accessed in the long-term and temporary storage. Depending on our needs, we can decide what to do with this information. We can choose to restructure some queries if we notice they result in a high system overhead. Or we can modify the limits and restrictions given to specific tenants based on how they interact with the system. The decision on how to act is left to the interpreter, but what the tracing system gives us is full information on how exactly the system is used and what impact does each interaction have on it.

Figure 12: Keeping track of data rejected by the *distributor*, viewing a specific trace

6 THINKING ABOUT THE FUTURE

The current distributed tracing infrastructure, as described in **Section 4**, has the capabilities of a proof-of-concept deployment, but it is not yet ready to be a full part of the monitoring service provided to all clients. It is a part of the production environment of the CERN monitoring infrastructure, but at this state, it is prepared only to serve clients that are maintained within the monitoring team itself. In order to be able to provide distributed tracing as a service to any client at CERN in the future, we must tackle a few additional challenges. These challenges include providing support for multitenancy and adapting the distributed tracing infrastructure in such a way that it natively fits together with the remainder of the monitoring infrastructure, providing a unified way of handling all monitoring data (logs, metrics and traces). In this section we will talk about these challenges in further detail, as well as about the ongoing efforts to restructure the current monitoring infrastructure, described in **Section 2**, and about the steps taken towards preparing the distributed tracing infrastructure for the eventual integration with this evolved version of the monitoring infrastructure.

A. MULTITENANCY

By providing distributed tracing only to client applications maintained by our team, we avoid the issue of data ownership. All of the data generated this way belongs to the monitoring team and, as long as the deployed services are accessible only within the team, all data can be gathered, processed, stored and presented together, without the need to think about access restrictions. When offering the possibility to use distributed tracing to any client within CERN, this stops being the case, and the system needs to be adapted in such a way to support multitenancy. Each client application then belongs to a specific tenant, and that tenant is the only one that has rights to access this data at any stage of its existence. This means that the data needs to be separated by tenant when it's gathered, processed, stored and presented. In order to achieve this, the distributed tracing infrastructure needs to be adapted accordingly:

- **Gathering** - At the collection entry point of the distributed tracing system, which is currently the **Jaeger Collector**, authentication and authorization must be added. This would ensure that, in order to send tracing data into the system, the client would have to provide proper credentials, identifying the tenant and thus the exact privileges it has.
- **Processing** - After entering the system, the data must be properly labeled such that it contains the information about the tenant it belongs to. This information should then define exactly which processing pipeline this data would follow inside the distributed tracing system.
- **Storage** - After being processed, the data must be stored in such a way that all data from one tenant is accessible at the storage layer (for reading or for writing) by that tenant and that tenant only.
- **Presentation** - At the presentation entry point of the distributed tracing system, which are currently **Jaeger UI** and **Grafana**, authentication and authorization must be added in such a way that the data belonging to a specific tenant can only be visualized if the proper credentials are provided.

As mentioned in the beginning of this section, the monitoring infrastructure is going through an evolution period and the distributed tracing infrastructure itself will have to evolve in order to natively fit within it. That is why the aforementioned multitenancy-related challenges will have to be evaluated specifically for the shape of the infrastructure used at the point when we decide to start offering distributed tracing as a service to all clients.

B. PREPARING FOR THE EVOLUTION OF THE MONITORING INFRASTRUCTURE

There is ongoing effort towards evolving the monitoring infrastructure described in **Section 2** in such a way that it follows the current industry trends and standards. The main ideas behind the evolution are - replacing the **Flume** components with instances of the **OpenTelemetry Collector** and adding **Fluent Bit** to the package of components provided out of the box to all CERN clients using the monitoring infrastructure. Since the goal is to eventually offer distributed tracing to all clients in a uniform way, like logs and metrics are currently offered, we need to prepare for this evolution from the perspective of the distributed tracing infrastructure as well. In order to do this, we conducted some experiments. The goal of the experiments was to test a few different configurations for the *producer* part of the distributed tracing infrastructure in order to understand which of them could be possible options for the future. The configurations included in the experiments were chosen in such a way to try to minimize the number of tracing-specific components used, and to try to utilize as many of the components we know will be a part of the monitoring infrastructure of the future. A visual representation of the configurations tested can be seen in **Figure 13**.

All of the experiments were conducted using **Grafana Mimir** as the client. **Grafana Mimir** uses the deprecated **Jaeger SDK** for Golang. The reason why we conducted our experiments with this client is that even though it is using a deprecated tracing library, it is a very important component of the monitoring infrastructure itself and we would like to keep the possibility of collecting traces from it. Additionally, integrating a client using a deprecated library is more challenging, considering there is a lack of support for the integration. Whereas, according to documentation, the integration of clients using the new **OpenTelemetry SDKs** should be entirely straightforward, and can thus be tested later.

Figure 13 depicts our experimental attempts towards evaluating the potential configurations for the *producer* part of the distributed tracing infrastructure of the future. Similarly as in **Figure 4**, in this figure, the existing parts of the monitoring infrastructure are depicted in orange, with dashed borders; the newly deployed elements are depicted in blue, with solid borders; the elements of the monitoring infrastructure of the future, currently used for testing this evolutionary step, are depicted in green, with borders following the dash-dot-dot pattern; and the elements maintained outside of

Figure 13: Visual representation of the different test configurations used

the monitoring team are depicted in black/gray, with borders following the dash-dot pattern. Each cluster is represented by a rectangle of different color, with a dotted boarder. The connections between components are represented with lines, where the black solid lines represent communication conducted without any encryption, and the green dashed lines represent communication encrypted using TLS. Each connection also has an associated label, containing a colon followed by a number, showing which port is used to establish it. When a cluster boundary is 'cut' with a component, that component depicts a port opened to the outside world; and the writing inside the component shows which type of authentication is used in order to establish a connection using that port. In the case when a component contained inside a cluster has a narrow wall on one of its sides, through which it makes connections, this means that the connection is made through a service, rather than to the component directly.

In the remainder of this subsection we will describe the four depicted experiments in further detail by discussing the idea behind each of them, the deployment methods and the results.

i. Experiment 1 - Removing the Jaeger Agent

The goal of the first experiment was to try to avoid the need for deploying a local instance of the **Jaeger Agent** in the cluster of the *client producer* in order to ensure communication with the remainder of the distributed tracing system. Thus, we tried connecting the client application directly to the **Jaeger Collector**.

The default **Jaeger Collector** port for accepting tracing data directly from the clients through HTTP is 14268. In order to enable the establishment of direct client connections, we needed to expose this Collector port in the same way port 14250 was exposed for the purpose of connecting through the **Jaeger Agent**. This connection was described in **Section 4.A.iv.**, and the details of the deployment of the corresponding route were described in **Section 4.B.ii.**

Similarly as in the case mentioned above, for the purpose of the deployment of this route, we need three OpenShift resources - an **Issuer**, a **Certificate** and a **Route**. However, here we only need to deploy a new **Certificate** and a new **Route**, while we can use the existing **Issuer**. The configuration

file used for the creation of these resources can be seen in **Listing 5**.

In this configuration file, we have the following values:

- `<jaeger_collector_client_hostname>` - The hostname through which this new Jaeger Collector endpoint will be accessible.
- `<collector_client_TLS_secret_name>` - The name of the secret holding the details about the certificate used to identify this Jaeger Collector route when establishing a TLS encrypted connection to it.

In addition to the previously described configuration, in order to enable the connection between Grafana Mimir and the Jaeger Collector, we needed to alter the Grafana Mimir deployment in such a way that it now has the following environment variable:

- `JAEGER_ENDPOINT=<jaeger_collector_client_hostname>:443`

This experiment proved to be successful, as we managed to receive and visualize traces sent directly from Grafana Mimir to the Jaeger Collector, without the need for the Jaeger Agent as the mediator.

ii. Experiments 2 and 3 - Connecting to the OpenTelemetry Collector

One of the key ideas behind the evolution of the monitoring infrastructure is replacing the Flume components with instances of the OpenTelemetry Collector (OTel Collector). On the *producer* side, this means that all monitoring data would be gathered by the OTel Collector, which would then place it into Kafka. Once inside Kafka, all different types of monitoring data can have their own processing pipelines. In order to conform to this standard, we decided to test the possibility of gathering tracing data from Grafana Mimir inside the OTel Collector as well.

A test instance of the OTel Collector is already running inside the monitoring infrastructure, and it is configured to send all monitoring data further into Kafka. Thus in order to ensure the tracing data reaches Kafka as well, we need to ensure it travels from Grafana Mimir to the OTel Collector. In order to do this, we altered the configuration of the OTel Collector by adding the necessary Jaeger Receiver, and including it into the `traces` pipeline. The snippet of the configuration that was changed can be seen below:

```
receivers:
  jaeger:
    protocols:
      thrift_binary:
        endpoint: <otel_machine_address>:14268
      thrift_http:
        endpoint: <otel_machine_address>:14269
      grpc:
        endpoint: <otel_machine_address>:14250
service:
  pipelines:
    traces:
      receivers: [ ... , jaeger]
```


In this snippet, `<otel_machine_address>` is the IP address of the OTel Collector virtual machine. The three ports mentioned in the snippet (14268, 14269 and 14250) were also properly exposed inside the virtual machine itself, such that they can be accessed from the outside.

After this, we tested two different ways of connecting Grafana Mimir to the OTel Collector - Directly (in **Experiment 2**) and using a Jaeger Agent (in **Experiment 3**). In **Experiment 2**, the connection was established using the following Grafana Mimir environment variable:

- `JAEGER_ENDPOINT=<otel_machine_address>:14268`

And in **Experiment 3**, the configuration of Grafana Mimir and the deployment of the Jaeger Agent were done in the same way as described in **Section 4.B.iii.**. The only difference being the following snippet from the configuration of the Jaeger Agent Deployment:

```
spec:
  template:
    spec:
      containers:
        - name: jaeger-agent
          args:
            - "--reporter.grpc.host-port=<otel_machine_address>:14250"
```

Where the value of the `-reporter.grpc.host-port` argument was adapted to point to the OTel Collector virtual machine, instead of the Jaeger Collector.

These two experiments proved to be unsuccessful as neither of these configurations resulted in traces from Grafana Mimir being delivered to Kafka. Neither Grafana Mimir, nor OpenTelemetry, nor Jaeger gave any logs with regard to why this connection is not working. In **Experiment 3** we were able to observe that the traces were indeed arriving to the OTel Collector machine on the correct port, but the OTel Collector itself has shown no sign of receiving the traces.

iii. Experiment 4 - Using Fluent Bit as an agent

Finally, **Experiment 4** is an attempt to bring everything together. Amongst the ideas behind the evolution of the monitoring infrastructure is the one to add Fluent Bit to the package of components provided out of the box to all CERN clients using the monitoring infrastructure. That is why, in **Experiment 4** we try to use Fluent Bit as the mediator for the connection between Grafana Mimir and the OTel Collector. This way, we remove the need for deploying a tracing-specific instance close to the client (Jaeger Agent), and we make establishing the connection to the OTel Collector easier, because Fluent Bit has integrated support for an OpenTelemetry output.

On the input side, Fluent Bit provides support for a long list of different input types. However, none of them are specific to Jaeger Tracing. Since this connection on the input side of Fluent Bit is not native, we focused our experiment on this specific problem and used standard output as the output mechanism. After careful analysis of the available input types, we concluded that the best attempt would be to use the HTTP input for Fluent Bit and try to instruct Grafana Mimir to send its traces there.

In order to deploy Fluent Bit in the Kubernetes cluster where Grafana Mimir is located, we used a ConfigMap resource to describe the configuration, a Deployment resource for the deployment itself and a corresponding Service resource. The configuration files used for the creation of these resources can be seen in **Listing 6** and **Listing 7**.

In these configuration files `<client_producer_namespace>` is the name of the Kubernetes namespace in which the *client producer* resides, and the `<configuration>` is a placeholder for the desired configuration details of the Fluent Bit component. The configuration used can be seen below:


```
[SERVICE]
  Daemon Off
  Log_Level Debug
  HTTP_Server On
  HTTP_Listen 0.0.0.0
  HTTP_Port 2020
  Health_Check On

[INPUT]
  Name http
  Tag jaeger
  Port 9880

[OUTPUT]
  Name stdout
  Match *
```

The settings used for the **Service** are the default settings, with the addition of increasing the log verbosity level to *Debug* so we can better analyze what is going on. The **Input** is set to type HTTP, on port 9880, and all traffic received this way is tagged as *'jaeger'*. The **Output** is set to standard output for any and all received data.

In the configuration file of the **Service** resource in Kubernetes, found in **Listing 7**, we make sure to expose port 9880 such that data can be freely sent to it.

After completing the aforementioned configuration, what remains is to direct **Grafana Mimir** to send its tracing data to the exposed endpoint of **Fluent Bit**. We attempted to do this in two different ways. The first attempt included setting the following environment variable for **Grafana Mimir**:

- `JAEGER_ENDPOINT=fluentbit-service.<client_producer_namespace>.svc.cluster.local:9880`

And the second attempt included setting the following environment variables:

- `JAEGER_AGENT_HOST=fluentbit-service.<client_producer_namespace>.svc.cluster.local`
- `JAEGER_AGENT_PORT='9880'`

Sadly neither of these attempts resulted in traces from **Grafana Mimir** reaching the standard output. Additionally, there were no logs inside **Grafana Mimir**, nor **Fluent Bit** regarding why that might be the case. The assumption is that the tracing data coming from **Grafana Mimir** doesn't have the format required by the **Fluent Bit** HTTP input and is thus being rejected.

iv. Takeaways

The conclusion from the previously described set of experiments described is that in the current state of things, connecting *client producer* applications using the deprecated **Jaeger** SDK with the monitoring infrastructure planned for the future is not feasible in a standardized and uniform way. As we prepare for the evolution of the monitoring infrastructure, we must take this into account and keep track of how the implementation of the relevant *client producer* applications changes over time. If applications like **Grafana Mimir** replace the deprecated **Jaeger** SDK with the **OpenTelemetry** SDK, it will be possible to natively integrate them with the infrastructure we wish to build. However, if such a thing doesn't happen soon enough, we will need to adjust the shape of the new monitoring infrastructure in such a way to make space for the components necessary for enabling this connection.

7 CONCLUSIONS

The integration of distributed tracing signals, using frameworks such as OpenTelemetry and Jaeger Tracing, represents a notable enhancement of the CERN Monitoring Infrastructure. The resulting advanced visualization capabilities, gained through Jaeger UI and Grafana, provide a basis for a more detailed understanding of system interactions, thus improving the ability to effectively diagnose and resolve issues in a particularly complex distributed system.

In order to achieve the goals of this project, we have addressed several technical challenges. These include deploying tracing-specific components in a naturally distributed environment, securing communication channels and configuring connections to clients, highlighting the importance of both functionality and security in monitoring frameworks.

Looking ahead, we also identify crucial areas for further development. Adapting the system for multitenancy and ensuring its compatibility with the evolving monitoring infrastructure at CERN are significant aspects that require attention in the future. The experimental approach taken to test different configurations is particularly informant with regard to the exact directionality of future steps. Thus ensuring that the eventual integration of distributed tracing into the CERN monitoring infrastructure of the future is done adequately.

At the given moment, the distributed tracing infrastructure created as a part of this project lives within the production environment of the monitoring infrastructure at CERN in the context of the *Monitoring-of-Monitoring (MoM)* part of the system. It provides the monitoring team with additional information about the monitoring system itself, allowing for introspection and simultaneously offering an opportunity to gain a deeper understanding of the capabilities distributed tracing has to offer. For the time being, this setup will continue to function within the *MoM* context only, until all necessary conditions, as outlined in the previous sections of this report, are met. Once these conditions are fulfilled, we anticipate expanding the availability of distributed tracing beyond the monitoring team, aiming to make it an integral and universally accessible component of the CERN monitoring system.

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CONFIGURATION FILES

```

1 storage:
2   type: elasticsearch
3   elasticsearch:
4     host: <opensearch_cluster_address>
5     port: 443
6     scheme: https
7     user: <os_internal_user_name>
8     usePassword: true
9     existingSecret: <os_internal_user_password_secret_name>
10    existingSecretKey: <os_internal_user_password_secret_key>
11    tls:
12      enabled: true
13      secretName: <OS_CA_Certificate_secret>
14  provisionDataStore:
15    cassandra: false
16    elasticsearch: false
17  agent:
18    enabled: false
19    cmdlineParams:
20      reporter.grpc.host-port: <jaeger_collector_hostname>:443
21      reporter.grpc.tls.enabled: "true"
22  collector:
23    extraEnv:
24      - name: COLLECTOR_GRPC_TLS_ENABLED
25        value: "true"
26      - name: COLLECTOR_GRPC_TLS_KEY
27        value: /tls/<collector_TLS_secret_RSA_key>
28      - name: COLLECTOR_GRPC_TLS_CERT
29        value: /tls/<collector_TLS_secret_certificate_key>
30    extraSecretMounts:
31      - name: route-tls
32        mountPath: /tls
33        subPath: ""
34        secretName: <collector_TLS_secret_name>
35      readOnly: true

```

Listing 1: values.yaml - Deployment of the Jaeger components using a Helm chart


```

1  apiVersion: cert-manager.io/v1
2  kind: Issuer
3  metadata:
4    name: certificate-issuer
5  spec:
6    acme:
7      privateKeySecretRef:
8        name: <acme_private_key_secret_name>
9      server: <encryption_server_address>
10     solvers:
11     - http01:
12       ingress:
13         serviceType: ClusterIP
14         ingressTemplate:
15           metadata:
16             annotations:
17               haproxy.router.openshift.io/ip_whitelist: ""
18         selector: {}
19 ---
20 apiVersion: cert-manager.io/v1
21 kind: Certificate
22 metadata:
23   name: route-certificate
24 spec:
25   dnsNames:
26   - <jaeger_collector_hostname>
27   issuerRef:
28     group: cert-manager.io
29     kind: Issuer
30     name: certificate-issuer
31   secretName: <collector_TLS_secret_name>
32   usages:
33   - digital signature
34   - key encipherment
35 ---
36 apiVersion: route.openshift.io/v1
37 kind: Route
38 metadata:
39   name: jaeger-collector
40 spec:
41   host: <jaeger_collector_hostname>
42   port:
43     targetPort: 14250
44   to:
45     kind: Service
46     name: jaeger-collector
47   tls:
48     termination: passthrough

```

Listing 2: collector-route.yaml - The OpenShift resources needed to properly expose a Jaeger Collector endpoint for connections with Jaeger Agent components


```
1  apiVersion: apps/v1
2  kind: Deployment
3  metadata:
4    name: jaeger-agent
5    namespace: <client_producer_namespace>
6  spec:
7    replicas: 1
8    selector:
9      matchLabels:
10     app: jaeger-agent
11   template:
12     metadata:
13       labels:
14         app: jaeger-agent
15     spec:
16       containers:
17         - name: jaeger-agent
18           image: jaegertracing/jaeger-agent:latest
19           imagePullPolicy: IfNotPresent
20           args:
21             - "--reporter.grpc.host-port=<jaeger_collector_hostname>:443"
22             - "--reporter.grpc.tls.enabled=true"
23           ports:
24             - containerPort: 5778
25               name: config-rest
26               protocol: TCP
27             - containerPort: 6831
28               name: jg-compact-trft
29               protocol: UDP
30             - containerPort: 6832
31               name: jg-binary-trft
32               protocol: UDP
33             - containerPort: 14271
34               name: admin-http
35               protocol: TCP
```

Listing 3: jaeger-agent-deployment.yaml - The Kubernetes Deployment for the Jaeger Agent component


```
1  apiVersion: v1
2  kind: Service
3  metadata:
4    name: jaeger-agent-service
5    namespace: <client_producer_namespace>
6    labels:
7      app: jaeger-agent
8  spec:
9    selector:
10     app: jaeger-agent
11   ports:
12     - name: jaeger-compact-thrift
13       protocol: UDP
14       port: 6831
15       targetPort: 6831
16     - name: jaeger-binary-thrift
17       protocol: UDP
18       port: 6832
19       targetPort: 6832
20     - name: jaeger-admin-http
21       protocol: TCP
22       port: 14271
23       targetPort: 14271
24     - name: jaeger-config-rest
25       protocol: TCP
26       port: 5778
27       targetPort: 5778
```

Listing 4: jaeger-agent-service.yaml - The Kubernetes Service for the Jaeger Agent component


```
1  apiVersion: cert-manager.io/v1
2  kind: Certificate
3  metadata:
4    name: route-certificate-direct
5  spec:
6    dnsNames:
7    - <jaeger_collector_client_hostname>
8    issuerRef:
9      group: cert-manager.io
10     kind: Issuer
11     name: certificate-issuer
12     secretName: <collector_client_TLS_secret_name>
13     usages:
14     - digital signature
15     - key encipherment
16  ---
17  apiVersion: route.openshift.io/v1
18  kind: Route
19  metadata:
20    name: jaeger-collector-direct
21  spec:
22    host: <jaeger_collector_client_hostname>
23    port:
24      targetPort: 14268
25    to:
26      kind: Service
27      name: jaeger-collector
28    tls:
29      termination: passthrough
```

Listing 5: collector-client-route.yaml - The OpenShift resources needed to properly expose a Jaeger Collector endpoint for direct connections with clients


```
1  apiVersion: v1
2  kind: ConfigMap
3  metadata:
4    name: fluentbit-config
5    namespace: <client_producer_namespace>
6  data:
7    fluent-bit.conf: <configuration>
8  ---
9  apiVersion: apps/v1
10 kind: Deployment
11 metadata:
12   name: fluentbit
13   namespace: <client_producer_namespace>
14 spec:
15   replicas: 2
16   selector:
17     matchLabels:
18       app: fluentbit
19   template:
20     metadata:
21       labels:
22         app: fluentbit
23     spec:
24       containers:
25         - name: fluentbit
26           image: fluent/fluent-bit:1.8
27           volumeMounts:
28             - name: config
29               mountPath: /fluent-bit/etc/
30       resources:
31         limits:
32           memory: 200Mi
33         requests:
34           cpu: 100m
35           memory: 100Mi
36       volumes:
37         - name: config
38           configMap:
39             name: fluentbit-config
```

Listing 6: fluentbit-deployment.yaml - The Kubernetes Deployment and ConfigMap for the Fluent Bit component


```
1  apiVersion: v1
2  kind: Service
3  metadata:
4    name: fluentbit-service
5    namespace: <client_producer_namespace>
6  spec:
7    selector:
8      app: fluentbit
9    ports:
10     - protocol: TCP
11       port: 24224
12       targetPort: 24224
13     - protocol: TCP
14       port: 9880
15       targetPort: 9880
```

Listing 7: fluentbit-service.yaml - The Kubernetes Service for the Fluent Bit component

